

A new locality of the rare snail *Plectostoma tonkinianum* (Dautzenberg & Fisher, 1905) (Gastropoda: Caenogastropoda: Diplommatidae) in Southern Vietnam

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Abstract: We confirm the occurrence of the rare species *Plectostoma tonkinianum* (Dautzenberg & Fisher, 1905) in Vietnam with a new georeferenced locality.

Keywords: *Plectostoma*, new records, Southeastern Indochinese Peninsula

Introduction

In old literature (19th and beginning of 20th centuries) many of the published species records are from localities whose names are presently changed. Additionally, because of borders changing, many of the old areas, such as “Cochinchina”, “Annam”, “Tonkin”, today are divided in different countries (Schileyko, 2011). For example, the French protectorate “Tonkin”, from where the type locality of *Plectostoma tonkinianum* (Dautzenberg & Fisher, 1905) is, presently covers territories in Southern China and the northern parts of Laos and Vietnam (Liew et al., 2014).

Up to now, the genus *Plectostoma* was assumed to be present in Vietnam with a single species – *P. tonkinianum*. Based on the analysis of the information in the old work of Dautzenberg & Fisher (1905), Liew et al. (2014) suggests that “*P. tonkinianum* probably occurs in the small limestone hills in the coastal areas of the southern part of Vietnam and neighbouring Cambodia.” Our finding confirms this suggestion.

Material and methods

The material was collected via the soil-sifting procedure (Antonova et al., 2015).

The specimens are stored in the mollusc’s collection of the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Sofia (Coll. ID 40334/9, adult specimens A-O).

Results and discussion

Plectostoma tonkinianum (Dautzenberg & Fisher, 1905) (Fig. 2)

Material examined: Southern Vietnam, Kien Giang Province, Kien Luong District, Binh An Commune, Ba Nui Village, area around the Mo So Cave (Fig. 1), N10.227652°, E104.616249°, 17 m a.s.l., limestone rocks, 18.IX.2018, leg. I. Dedov, N. Simov, R. Bekchiev, P. Beron, 15 adult and 11 juvenile shells.

Fig. 1. Locality of the species *Plectostoma tonkinianum* (Dautzenberg & Fisher, 1905), Southern Vietnam, Kien Giang Province, area of the Mo So Cave. Photo: I. K. Dedov.

The collected specimens perfectly fit to the species description, given by Liew et al. (2014, p 60–61, fig. 26 A–H) and were found in the area, suggested by the authors.

Liew et al. (2014) indicated the conservation status of the species as DD – data deficient, because of lack of information for the habitat and population status of the species. We found *P. tonkinianum* in the touristic area near the Mo So Cave. At the same time, in the neighbouring limestone hills open quarries were observed. In our opinion, in the case with such small and rare animals, inhabiting in the soil and rock crevices, touristic use of the habitat is more protective. Therefore, opening new quarries in the areas of occurrence of rare species such as *P. tonkinianum*, should be regulated and even forbidden.

Creating georeferenced localities and clarifying the descriptions of many of the species described from Vietnam and the whole Indochina remains an important task for the malacologists.

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Fig. 2. *Plectostoma tonkinianum* (Dautzenberg & Fisher, 1905): frontal, lateral, and posterior views of the shell. Photo: I. K. Dedov.

lecting trip in Vietnam; to Ulrich E. Schneppat who supplied us with literature; as well as to the two anonymous reviewers for the helpful remarks.

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